

Can Task Observation Manipulate for Optic Flow during Treadmill Gait Training in Stroke Patients? A randomized controlled trial.

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Abstract

Background: Treadmill training is used for gait rehabilitation after stroke. One of the drawbacks of this technique is that optic flow which is required for normal walking pattern is lost. Optic flow has been modulated using virtual reality system. However, this system is costly and uses a sophisticated technology that may require great skills to operate. We therefore hypothesized that observing another person doing treadmill training while a patient is doing treadmill gait training can manipulate for optic flow.

Aim: The aim of this study was to compare a group of stroke patients who will do treadmill gait training plus task observation and another who will do treadmill gait training alone. **Method:** Nine participants were randomized into control group (treadmill only, n=5) and the experimental group (treadmill + task observation, n=4). In each group, the training was done for 30 minutes per session in bouts of 10 minutes with 5 minutes rests in between, 3 times a week for 4 weeks. Data for step length, stride length and walking speed were collected at baseline, 2 weeks and 4 weeks post-intervention and analyzed using independent t-test for between and repeated measures ANOVA for within group data. **Result:** The results showed significant improvement only in stride length within group in the experimental group and in walking speed between group in favour of the experimental group post-intervention ($p < 0.05$). **Conclusion:** There is an indication that task observation can manipulate optic flow during treadmill gait training as it improved stride length and walking speed in the experimental group.

Keywords: Stroke, treadmill training, optic flow, motor recovery, lower limb and task repetition

Introduction

Stroke is a condition that can cause long term disability in walking. The disability in walking following stroke has been said to occur in majority of cases [1]; and it is a consequence of impairment in gait parameters such as step length, stride length and walking speed. For the rehabilitation of gait impairment after stroke, there are many techniques which are being used. These techniques include overground and treadmill gait trainings [2]. The overground gait training involves patients walking overground and receiving feedback and guidance under the supervision of a therapist. However, overground gait training does not have sufficient evidence for effectiveness at improving gait parameters [3]; and it seems not to involve high task repetition that is necessary for appreciable motor learning.

Treadmill gait training on the other hand is a form of task oriented training and it provides a passive high repetition of walking movement. Studies of treadmill gait training either with or without bodyweight support have shown evidence of its effectiveness in terms of improving movement impairment and gait parameters [4-7].

However, during treadmill training, there is loss of optic flow [8]. Optic flow is a sensation of body movement at the eyes during normal walking; and it is important for coupling with foot proprioception to produce a normal walking pattern [9-10].

To improve the loss of optic flow during treadmill gait training, a head mounted display and virtual reality system has been used with success [8, 10-12]. However, virtual reality system uses a sophisticated technology that could be costly and requires great skills to operate. In place of the virtual reality system, we therefore propose the use of task observation. This involves observing a second person doing treadmill gait training while at the same time the observer is doing treadmill gait training. We hypothesized that, when one observes another person performing treadmill gait training at the same time he is doing treadmill gait training; the movement of the second person's body will give the observer a perception of body movement in the eye. We therefore aimed to compare a group of stroke patients who will do treadmill gait training plus task observation and another who will do treadmill gait training alone.

Figure 1: The Study Flowchart

Material and Methods

The study was a randomized controlled trial (RCT) evaluating the effectiveness of treadmill gait training combined with observation of treadmill gait training and treadmill gait training alone on gait parameters (step length, stride length and walking speed) in stroke patients. The study was approved by Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital Research Ethics Committee.

The study population was stroke patients attending Physiotherapy at Aminu Kano Teaching Hospital in Kano, Nigeria. Patients were included in the study if they were stroke patients who have the ability to walk with little or no support, patients who gave their consent to participate in the study, patients with no significant cognitive impairment (Minimental state examination score ≥ 17) and those with no significant risk of fall (Tinetti gait and balance score ≥ 19).

The instruments used for the data collection in the study include 2 treadmill machines, stop watch, tape measure, 2 bottles of ink, masking tape, cotton wool, 10 meter long white floor paper, Minimental state examination scale and Tinetti gait and balance scale.

The Tinetti gait and balance scale assesses gait and balance. It is scored on a 3 point ordinal scale [13]. In stroke patients, it demonstrated high test-retest reliability and has moderate construct validity with motor Functional Independence Measure [14]. The Minimental state examination scale is used to assess mental state or cognitive ability [15]. It is reported to have good test-retest and internal consistency, and current validity with scales measuring similar construct [16-17]. Outcomes were measured at baseline, 2 weeks and 4 weeks post-intervention by one of the authors (NSA).

A total of 20 stroke patients were screened for eligibility to participate in the study. Out of this number, 8 were excluded for not fulfilling the study inclusion criteria, and the remaining 12 qualified to be included in the study. However, 3 patients eventually declined consent. Therefore, the remaining 9 patients were randomized using simple random sampling involving the use of sealed envelopes into the control group (treadmill only, $n=5$) and the experimental group (treadmill + task observation, $n=4$). See figure 1 for more information on the study flowchart (Figure 1)

The study participants in the experimental group were paired into 2 groups with each group members on

treadmills facing each other. The participants were asked to observe each other while doing the treadmill training. The control group however did treadmill training without observing another person training on a treadmill. In each group, the training was done for 30 minutes per session in bouts of 10 minutes with 5 minutes rests in between, 3 times a week for 4 weeks. The data for the study was collected at baseline, 2 weeks and 4 weeks post-intervention.

The data obtained in the study was analyzed using descriptive statistics for the demographics, independent t-test for between group data and repeated measures ANOVA for within group data. In each case, the effect sizes were also calculate.

Results

A total of 9 participants completed the study (control, n=5 and experimental, n=4). Inferential statistics showed that, there were significant differences between groups in age, sex, time since stroke, type of stroke and side affected. See table 1 for the details of these analyses and the demographic characteristics of the study participants.

Determination of within group differences using one-way repeated ANOVA

Result for step length

For the control group, there was no significant difference in step length between baseline, 2 weeks and 4 weeks post-intervention Wilk's lambda=0.63, $F(2,5)=2.38$, $p=0.20$, multi-variate partial eta squared=0.37. Similarly, for the experimental group, there was no significant difference in step length between baseline, 2 weeks and 4 weeks post-intervention, Wilk's lambda=0.11, $F(2,4)=7.88$, $p=0.11$, multivariate partial eta squared=0.89. The details of the results of this analysis are presented in table 2.

Result for stride length

For the control group, there was no significant difference in stride length between baseline, 2 weeks and 4 weeks post-intervention, Wilk's lambda=0.16, $F(2,5)=7.70$, $p=0.07$, multivariate partial eta squared =0.84. However for the experimental group, there was significant difference in stride length between baseline, 2 weeks and 4 weeks, Wilk's lambda=0.17, $F(2,4)=14.31$, $p=0.03$, multivariate partial eta squared=0.83. The result of this analysis is also presented in table 2. Since there was significant difference between the 3 time points, a Bonferonni posthoc analysis was used to determine where the difference exists. The sub-group analysis revealed a significant difference only between baseline and 4 weeks (mean difference= 0.00, 95% CI: 0.000 to 0.000, $p=0.000$)

Result for walking speed

For the control group, there was no significant difference in walking speed between baseline, 2 weeks and 4 weeks post-intervention, Wilk's lambda=0.13, $F(2,5)=10.24$, $p=0.05$, multi-variate partial eta squared=0.87. Similarly, for the experimental group, there was no significant difference in walking speed between baseline, 2 weeks and 4 weeks post-intervention, Wilk's lambda=0.30, $F(2,4)=2.32$, $p=0.30$, multivariate partial eta squared=0.70. The details of the results of this analysis are presented in table 2 (Table 2).

Differences in step length, stride length and walking speed between control and experimental groups at baseline, 2 weeks and 4 weeks post-intervention.

Result for step length

At baseline, there was no significant difference between the control (mean=0.31, SD=0.09) and experimental (mean=0.29, SD=0.07) $t(7) =0.32$, $p=0.76$ two-tailed. The magnitude of the difference in the mean (mean difference=-0.18, 95% CI; -0.11 to 0.15) was very small, eta squared=0.01. At 2 weeks, there was no significant difference between the control (mean=0.34, SD=0.91) and experimental (mean=0.32, SD=0.05) $t(7) =0.34$, $p=0.75$ two-tailed. The magnitude of the difference in the mean (mean difference=-0.34, 95% CI; -0.10 to 0.13) was very small, eta squared=0.01. At 4 weeks, there was no significant difference between the control (mean=0.34, SD=0.91) and experimental (mean=0.32, SD=0.05) $t(7) =0.26$, $p=0.81$ two-tailed. The magnitude of the difference in the mean (mean difference=0.01, 95% CI; -0.11 to 0.13) was very large, eta squared=9.56. See table 3 for more details (Table 3)

Result for stride length

At baseline, there was no significant difference between the control (mean=0.61, SD=0.20) and experimental (mean=0.60, SD=0.12) $t(7) =0.10$, $p=0.93$ two-tailed. The magnitude of the difference in the mean (mean difference=0.01, 95% CI; -0.25 to 0.27) was very small, eta squared=0.00. At 2 weeks, there was no significant difference between the control (mean=0.67, SD=0.18) and experimental (mean=0.64, SD=0.10) $t(7) =0.30$, $p=0.77$ two-tailed. The magnitude of the difference in the mean (mean difference=-0.31, 95% CI; -0.20 to 0.26) was very small, eta squared=0.01. At 4 weeks, there was no significant difference between the control (mean=0.69, SD=0.17) and experimental (mean=0.60, SD=0.12) $t(7) =0.97$, $p=0.38$ two-tailed. The magnitude of the difference in the mean (mean difference=0.09, 95% CI; -0.13 to 0.32) was very small, eta squared=0.12. See table 3 for more details (Table 3).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Study Participants. Key: M/F=Male/Female, I/H=Ischaemic/Haemorrhagic, R/L=Right/Left

SN	Variable	Control (n=5)	Experimental (n=4)	p-value
1	Age	51.40±1.60	47.75±2.75	0.18
2	Sex (M/F)	3/2	4/0	0.41
3	Time since stroke	10.20±2.83	12.25±2.99	0.31
4	Type of stroke (I/H)	5/0	2/2	0.56
5	Side affected (R/L)	4/1	3/1	0.56

Result for walking speed

At baseline, there was a significant difference between the control (mean=0.41, SD=0.10) and experimental (mean=0.59, SD=0.11) $t(7) = -2.57$, $p=0.04$ two-tailed. The magnitude of the difference in the mean (mean difference=-0.18, 95% CI; -0.25 to 0.27) was very small, $\eta^2=0.37$. At 2 weeks, there was a significant difference between the control (mean=0.45, SD=0.11) and experimental (mean=0.64, SD=0.16) $t(7) = -2.51$, $p=0.04$ two-tailed. The magnitude of the difference in the mean (mean difference=-0.20, 95% CI; -0.0 to 0.26) was moderate, $\eta^2=0.47$. At 4 weeks, there was a significant difference between the control (mean=0.45, SD=0.11) and experimental (mean=0.64, SD=0.16) $t(7) = -2.46$, $p=0.04$ two-tailed. The magnitude of the difference in the mean (mean difference=0.06, 95% CI; -0.13 to 0.32) was very small, $\eta^2=0.00$. See table 3 for more details. (Table 3)

Discussion

The result of this study showed that there was only significant improvement in stride length from baseline to 2 and 4 weeks post-intervention in the experimental group, but not in step length and walking speed. In contrast, there was no significant improvement from baseline to 2 and 4 weeks post-intervention in all the outcomes in the control group.

For between groups, there was only a significant difference in walking speed post-intervention in favour of the experimental group. However, the experimental group had a higher walking speed at baseline.

Treadmill gait training varies with overground walking for it lacks the optic flow which is usually coupled with proprioception in the foot to produce normal move

ment [8-10]. In the literature, virtual reality and other hi-tech systems have been used to modulate optic flow and optimize normal walking during treadmill gait training [8, 10-12]. However, these hi-tech systems are costly and sophisticated and may have the potential of being limited to only laboratory uses. Consequently, we hypothesized that, observing another person doing treadmill gait training, while a patient is doing treadmill gait training, may provide him with an illusion of optic flow. This technique is simple, less costly and seems to be tolerated by the patients.

From the findings thus far, there seems to be a benefit of task observation in walking speed and stride length in the experimental group, indicating possible modulation of optic flow. Similarly, previous studies have reported improved balance and gait parameters when optic flow was modulated using virtual reality system and head mounted display [8, 12]. Additionally, in conditions other than stroke such as Parkinson's disease, walking speed and stride length were improved with the separate use of structured speed-dependent treadmill training and limited progressive treadmill training [18].

Although our study indicates a relevance of the use of task observation in modulation of optic flow during treadmill gait training, we recommend further investigation on a larger sample to further verify the usefulness of the technique.

Conclusion

There is an indication that task observation can manipulate optic flow during treadmill gait training as it improves stride length and walking speed in the experimental group. However, further studies are needed to provide a strong evidence base for our claim.

Table 2: Differences in step length, stride length and walking speed between baseline, 2 weeks and 4 weeks Post-intervention in the control and experimental groups

Scale	Time period	n	Mean±SD	Control F	p-value	Time period	n	Mean±SD	Experimental F	p-values
Step length	Baseline	5	0.31±0.09	2.38	0.20	Baseline	4	0.29±0.07	7.88	0.11
	2 weeks	5	0.34±0.91			2 weeks	4	0.32±0.05		
	4 weeks	5	0.34±0.91			4 weeks	4	0.32±0.05		
Stride length	Baseline	5	0.61±0.20	7.70	0.07	Baseline	4	0.60±0.12	14.31	0.03
	2 weeks	5	0.67±0.18			2 weeks	4	0.64±0.10		
	4 weeks	5	0.69±0.17			4 weeks	4	0.60±0.12		
Walking speed	Baseline	5	0.41±0.10	10.24	0.05	Baseline	4	0.59±0.11	2.32	0.30
	2 weeks	5	0.45±0.11			2 weeks	4	0.64±0.13		
	4 weeks	5	0.45±0.11			4 weeks	4	0.68±0.16		

Table 3: Differences in step length, stride length and walking speed between control and experimental groups at baseline, 2 weeks and 4 weeks Post-intervention.

Scale	Time period	n	Control Mean±SD	n	Experimental Mean±SD	p-values
Step length	Baseline	5	0.31±0.09	4	0.29±0.07	0.76
	2 weeks	5	0.34±0.91	4	0.32±0.05	0.75
	4 weeks	5	0.34±0.91	4	0.32±0.05	0.81
Stride length	Baseline	5	0.61±0.20	4	0.60±0.12	0.93
	2 weeks	5	0.67±0.18	4	0.64±0.10	0.77
	4 weeks	5	0.69±0.17	4	0.60±0.12	0.38
Walking speed	Baseline	5	0.41±0.10	4	0.59±0.11	0.04
	2 weeks	5	0.45±0.11	4	0.64±0.13	0.04
	4 weeks	5	0.45±0.11	4	0.68±0.16	0.04

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Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.